

THE EMPIRICAL ILLUSION AND RECONSIDERING THE ESSENCE OF 'THE POLITICAL'

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This paper is an attempt to examine the methodology and dynamics of contemporary political theory. It never denies the constructive role of the empirical facts in theory building, but refutes the claims of circumventing the role of norms, values, preferences, in the understanding of 'the political'. This is also an attempt to identify why it is impossible to completely reject the normative framework due to the inherence of the antagonistic nature of human beings. It is the plurality, diverse and ever-contesting ideas, thoughts of human beings, what keep 'the political' alive. The age of post-truth politics creates a difficulty not only to find out the objective facts and truth, but also to understand the nuances of politics.

Prologue

It is often said that political theory is rather an ambiguous term in the discipline of political science as political theory is claimed by the both philosophical and scientific practitioners, as philosophical indicates the normative political theory, scientific refers to the empirical political theory. But, someone can say that there is an ambiguity with the name of the discipline political science because the term 'science' is pretty problematic here. If here science implies the scientific understanding of politics, it uncovers some vital questions; does this discipline enquire scientifically the nature and practices of politics adopting the methods based on quantification, verification, measurement, observation, description, etc., or does only the scientific explanation explore adequately the nature and practices of politics in local or national or international level, or does only the empirical data explain the essence of 'the political'? Even it discloses another questions that whether the scientific generalisation is fully applicable in understanding the nuances of politics and political, or any theoretical understanding is needed for analyzing spirit of the political? In this essay we intend to underline some methodological shades curious to how we will understand and analyse the underlying structure of 'the political'. Also this essay encapsulates why fully empirical study, discerning the human innate dimensions, is not capable of capturing the core of 'the political', however, this essay not fully ignores the

empirical study. Though this essay is not exclusively for the researchers of political science, yet we propose that the every political research should also be capable of capturing the nuances of 'the political', which are shaped by the antagonistic nature of the human beings. Finally, this essay focuses on the nature of 'the political' that demands a deeper understanding for explaining the empirical political reality, rather than merely explaining the fact collected and interpreting the data with the help of some 'designated' software as the conception of objective facts and truth have also been contested in contemporary political context.

Explaining or Interpreting 'The Political'?

Here we start with an important question that whether we can use 'politics' and 'the political' in a same sense or not. Chantal Mouffe says "political science which deals with the empirical field of 'politics', and political theory which is the domain of philosophers who enquire not about facts of 'politics' but about essence of 'the political'".¹ Martin Heidegger² posited a distinction between 'ontic' and 'ontology' as while the former is the study of the particular being and what the particular being can do, the latter is the study of the theory of a being. Ontical is always grounded on ontological. In other words, ontological is the foundation of ontical. If the ontic is real and concrete, the ontology is the theoretical understanding of the reality. Mouffe applies Heidegger's idea to make a distinction

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between 'politics' and 'the political', and says that while 'politics' denotes the 'ontic' level because it refers to the various practices of conventional politics, 'the political' refers to the 'ontological' one, means it is the foundation of the conventional practices of politics and constitutive of human societies.³ So, we can say that the theoretical understanding on 'the political', which is based on the antagonistic nature of human being, comes at primary concern in explaining the conventional practices of 'politics'. Therefore, any research in political science will not be viable unless addressing the fundamental or basic questions which are constitutive of the essence of 'the political'.

The very reason why use of the methodology of natural sciences is inapplicable to the study of social sciences, in the natural sciences they tend to focus on objectivity and generalisation but in social sciences there are no such things as universal laws or principles that will be applicable all over the world in a uniform way. Social sciences deal with human beings who are self-evaluative in nature, they learn from their historical past and act themselves in the changing situations. But in natural sciences if certain steps are followed carefully it will always yield similar results. It is well accepted that while the natural world continues independently of human being, the human world is largely instituted on human action which is unpredictable. Explanation always finds regularity to enquire not only the past but also the future. In other words, modern empirical sciences search for explaining the future through prediction.⁴ While the physical world can exist without any conceptual schema, the human world is profoundly conceptual since human beings do not merely live and sense it, but always try to create images, concepts, understand, and interpret the experiences. Human beings live in, what philosopher Edmund Husserl says, the 'life world'⁵ and plagiarizing the vocabulary of philosopher Wilhelm Dilthey we might say this experience as 'lived experience'. Wilhelm Dilthey argued for hermeneutics to comprehend the interpretations of human experiences and historical texts of human life. The word hermeneutics is derived from the Greek god *Hermes*, a deity of speech and writing. Dilthey strongly rejected in using a model formed exclusively for natural sciences and instead proposed developing a separate methodology for human sciences. His argument centered around the idea that in the natural sciences we seek to explain

phenomena in terms of cause and effect, in the human sciences, contrarily, we seek to understand and interpret the phenomena. In other words, while nature offers a field of explanation, humanity offers a field of understanding, in German what is called '*Verstehen*' and which is based on the 'lived experience'. Dilthey wrote, "understanding of other people and their expression is developed on the basis of experience and self-understanding and the constant interactions between them."⁶ We can find two conclusions from Dilthey – firstly, distinction between human sciences and natural sciences. In the domain of nature the rules are same, but in human society the rules vary over the time and space. Secondly, there is a difference between explanation and understanding. Since human beings are unpredictable then social sciences should not be describing or explaining method. It should be understanding and interpreting. Thus political theory is often assumed a hermeneutic experience and political theorists are termed hermeneuts who interpret events grounding in 'the political'. Auguste Comte, the founding figure of sociology and pioneer of positivism, himself insisted that "no real observation of any kind of phenomenon is possible, except in as far as it is first directed, and finally interpreted, by some theory."⁷ In social sciences, values and theorists' own experiences indeed play an important role. For example, if we do not understand or have experienced certain conceptions of justice how can we assess a fact as whether it is just or unjust? If we distinguish between good or bad we must have certain notion of good and bad and here theories play an important role in shaping individual preferences and their understanding of the social world. Indicating the limits of the translated works on Dilthey, Makkreel and Rodi prefaced in the 'Selected Works of Wilhelm Dilthey' as "Dilthey's overall position was more flexible than has been realised. His distinction between understanding (*Verstehen*) and explaining, for example, was not intended to exclude explanations from the human sciences, but only to delimit their scope."⁸ As far as *Verstehen* is concerned, Max Weber argued that all the sciences of psychological and social phenomena are science of human conduct including thoughts and attitudes of human beings, and "these sciences seek to understand this conduct and by means of this understanding to explain it interpretatively."⁹ In Politics, however, we do not only explain certain political realities only on the basis of the empirical evidences, but we explore

and interpret these political realities on the basis of theory. Notwithstanding explanation is crucial, but all theories are not explanatory and explanation is not the whole, but a part of political theory.¹⁰ This does not mean that we are free from biases but our goals should be that we must understand our biases and try as far as possible to develop a systematic body of work. In the twentieth century, due to remarkable transformation in both social as well as natural sciences research and with the development of falsification, the members of scientific community came to conclusion that only verification could not be regarded as the sole criterion of scientific knowledge because it is an ongoing process. So, going beyond causality as the only accepted method of verifying hypothesis, we should also give due place to the alternative models, as Gurpreet Mahajan says, i.e. reason-action explanation, narrative mode and hermeneutic understanding.¹¹ Even in an explanation, the observer must validate his claims by interpreting his outcomes and infer whether the outcomes are in accordance with his hypothesis that are conceptualised based on certain theoretical understanding or not. Thus Mahajan argues once we started to consider interpretation and presence of theory as a condition rather a limitation we can overcome and even develop a truly scientific body of knowledge that will make a bridge between methodologies of natural sciences with the normative framework upon which the whole human sciences rest.¹² Mere facts or information do not define or explain themselves, we need a framework of analysis that is constructed by theories that explain and provides meaning of the facts and makes these facts significant to discuss, evaluate, and deliberate about any social phenomenon. The relationship between theory and reality is an essential and complementary one. It is the theory or conceptual schema that provides the foundation that helps to evaluate the political reality easily, in return the evaluation helps to broaden the horizons of theory. As "it is impossible to understand thought or action or work without evaluating it. If we are unable to evaluate adequately, as we very frequently are, we have not yet succeeded in understanding adequately."¹³

The influx of behavioural revolution in political science calls for developing certain set of principles and *test* (verification or falsification) any *empirical* political phenomena by these principles for arriving at a valid *generalisation*, but the feasibility of this

approach, as accepted well is essentially faulted one. The empirical aspect upon which the behaviouralism emphasises profoundly is very different in explaining the phenomena of natural sciences and in the study of human sciences. It is already well argued that in natural sciences they are thought independent. In other words, events will occur naturally even we do not perceive this event by our conceptual understanding. For example, rainfall will occur naturally even we do not have a limited idea of what rainfall is, but in the study of human sciences it is the human being who perceives socio-political events through their understanding even perceiving the same phenomena very differently from one other. Not only that their existence essentially depends upon human beings' perception and conceptual understanding. For example, state, justice, rights, liberty, and equality, do not exist in physical form but they are thought dependent. It makes politics really unpredictable and for that reason developing a universal set of principles for explaining human political behaviour is really problematic, unattainable and impossible. The political theory thus helps us not only to explain the conventional practices of politics but to uncover the complexity by accompanying the conceptual framework by which we perceive the essence of 'the political'. So in this sense no theory in political science is completely true or false but that theory is more feasible and practical which explains and interprets better reconciling this fact-value dichotomy.

Foundation Shaken But Not Broken

In early 1950s, during the conquest of behaviouralism, the death or decline of political theory was announced.¹⁴ There is ample of literature which advocates that "either the death was prematurely diagnosed or that the wrong corpse was, in fact, identified."¹⁵ We must be familiar with what 'science' implies before comprehending why there is so much emphasis to enquire politics empirically by sidestepping its normative traits. David Easton points out some reasons responsible for decline of modern political theory, for example, too much emphasis on the transcendental nature of historical enquiry, its apathy to the causal theory, etc.¹⁶ At the same time, he acknowledges the role of values and says "values cannot be shed in the way a person removes his coat. They are an integral part of personality and as long as we are human, we can assume that our mental sets and preferences will be with us."¹⁷ Cobban¹⁸, while

commenting on the decline of political theory, argues that political theory as a tradition was not able to maintain its progressive character, but simultaneously he rejects the view that the contents of political theory have already been exhausted. On the contrary, he argues that every idea is essentially context driven and ideas change over the time. It grows and over the time it decays. Cobban regarding the nature of contemporary politics argues that the problem of contemporary understanding of political discourse is that it also suffers from lack of direction and of purposes while he underlines why there is a greater need of rational theory today. Theories have its own primacy in human sciences and even in natural sciences also what is often missed out by many. Question may arise that is it even possible for natural sciences to completely be value free? Or, what is the role of normative dimension in the discipline of natural sciences? Referring to the second question the major crux of any scientific study is the development of certain principles on the basis of which it tries to make generalisation but the question remains when a scientist develops a set of hypothesis, is it totally free from his own value preferences? The similar question may be asked that why a specific object of the natural world attracts the researcher to conduct analysis? Can we conceive it without understanding one's own value preferences? This parochial and narrow centric understanding of natural sciences, as Lekka-Kowalik critiques, lies in the fact that when natural sciences start to take values into account, it essentially constitutes an example of bad science due to the fact that natural sciences as a whole refers to an objective and value free analysis and understanding of the natural world that strives for developing certain set of rules with universal applicability.¹⁹ In spite of natural sciences' too much emphasis on this empirical side, even in reality, it is not possible to develop a systematic and scientific study while totally neglecting innate value preferences. Science in general is seen as a set of means or tools by which certain goals are achieved, these goals are essentially determined by the societal needs. The task of science is to efficiently achieve that goals in a more convenient way. But among several goals what goals require an urgent scientific remedy, here lies the value preferences. Similarly the question of ethics, morality, all of which are essentially value laden become too much apparent in case of misuse of science and technology. We often heard the phrase that is science a 'boon or blessing'? It implies, in spite

of too much emphasis on 'objectivity', science have a responsibility towards the well-being and good of the society. Lekka-Kowalik highlights an interesting area of value laden aspects of science. She identifies the role of scientific expertise in public-policy decision making where scientists must rely on certain choices, those choices range from using appropriate methodology to interpret their findings effectively.²⁰ This becomes even more apparent when they have to justify their outcomes by underlining why alternative choices are not feasible. But unfortunately we lay more emphasis on the findings rather than those choices which are essentially moulded by one's own preferences. So in short, as long as science has a progressive role to play in development of human race, it may claim for complete objective analysis but in reality natural sciences are not completely free from value preferences. The problem is that how we interpret the essence of science. Values in natural sciences are not explicit per se, they are moreover latent and implicit in nature that does not imply science is essentially value-free.

From the very beginning, political theory has been misinterpreted that it prescribes more or speculates much rather than comprehend the actual political realities, but this view is essentially mistaken one. The actual connotation of 'theory' is often miss-employed when we use the term 'political theory'. This trend has been in vogue since the nineteenth and twentieth centuries that it is being used pejoratively as corresponding to what Vincent identifies as 'mere speculation' or 'untested facts'.²¹ But if we look at the origin of the word 'theory' which is derived from the Greek words '*theoros*', one who performs as an envoy, and '*theoria*', the activity of *theoros*. Both '*theoros*' and '*theoria*' came from the word '*thea*' means to look upon or view. *Theoros* was employed to observe the foreign cultural and religious rituals. Besides observation *theoros* was supposed to report back to his native city. Then theory can be seen as the intermediary among the events, the observer, and interpretations. Theory thus implies essentially linkable with observational reality and its interpretations.²² Thiele observes "Theories help us put the world in focus. What optical lenses do for our vision, theories do for our understanding. Whereas optical lenses improve our sight, theories improve our insight."²³ Theories are conceptual schemas that bring a world into clearer focus and allow us to better

understand the world phenomena. Political theory represents "seeing" political phenomena in two senses. First, political theory provides a description of the political and second, political theory constitutes a form of aesthetic or religious vision. In the second sense political theory relates to the imaginative capacity of the theorist "an esemplastic" power that "forms all into once graceful intelligent whole."²⁴ Imagination is essential as no theorist have the capacity to observe all political phenomena directly.

Beyond Excessive Empiricism and Extreme Normativism

Over the years in the discourses of social sciences especially in the study of politics there are tendencies to separate theories, which are condemned to be more normative in nature, from the practical understanding of political reality. This empirical-normative dichotomy leads to the 'mad craze' of implementing scientific tools in explaining politics is essentially misguided. Robert Cox argues in this respect that this dichotomy is not simple as it seems every theorist intentionally or unintentionally brings certain values in their analysis that is why he says that we must look closely to those ideas that claim themselves to be objective or value free and ask who or what is it for and what purpose does it serve.²⁵ Pondering upon the need to resolve empirical-normative dichotomy or making a consolidation between the two, we may refer to the work of Amartya Sen. Amartya Sen falsifies the Rawlsian notion of justice on the ground that it is impossible to reach any society which is 'perfectly just.' He therefore calls for an alternative notion to find out that society which is comparatively 'less unjust.' He quests for 'removal of injustice' instead of making the institutions 'perfectly just.'²⁶ While Sen falsifies Rawlsian notion of justice, the question arises does Sen totally adopt a philosophical method to understand the causes of injustice, like famine, hunger, malnutrition, etc., in the third world countries? Rather he categorically rests upon an ample size of empirical or factual data that shapes his understanding on the idea of justice. In social sciences our focus should not confine only to problem identification but solution of these problems are essentially important one. It is often been said political philosophy prescribes more than tries to identify the solutions of the problems but we should keep in mind when we problematise something we must have certain conceptions or theories, and also we recommend some solutions with

the help of 'what ought to be'. We tend to focus more on data or information while looking for solutions but in order to rightly assess the problems and to provide solutions we need to have definite conceptual understanding of the problems and this conceptual understanding is undoubtedly value laden. So if we adopt problem solving approach in social sciences, it links values and facts. Theile holds that theories work well only when they efficiently deal with and make a tie between the received information and conceptual networks. Too little data or a scarcity of conceptual linkages lead to an underexposed image of the world. Information is required for the foundation of theory. Similarly too much data leads to an overexposed image of the world.²⁷ The normative standard enables us to reject the unnecessary facts and accept the necessary facts. While we protest against the human rights violation of a particular community, we should have the prerequisite knowledge on 'what is human rights?', 'why do we need it?', 'how it can be violated?', 'how can we say this *exact event* as human rights violation?'. Here the last question is based on empirical enquiry while the rest are conceptual and normative. Similarly when we speak of administrative corruption, we know well that the crisis of ethics in administration leads to a corrupt administration. We simultaneously apply concept and use data to prove it that why we can mark the *particular incident* as *corruption*. After identifying something as corruption we look forward to employing some necessary actions for removing or at least reducing it grounded on 'what ought to be.' Though some authors like Terence Ball opines that there should not be any 'perennial questions' in politics since the moral languages responsible for framing the questions are not historically transcendental.²⁸ but the authors like Robins opined that philosophical enquiry brings the issues like 'what is justice?', 'what is liberty?', 'why should we obey the state?', closely in our focus which are the 'perennial questions' in politics²⁹ and these remain important over the time because these are, we do believe, the foundations of the human world as well as retain the essence of 'the political'. Political philosophy is not merely for description and prescription rather the task of the political philosophers is to identify problems and finding out the ways by means of which we can get rid of these problems more efficiently. The more discrepancy between 'what is' and 'what ought to be', the more challenge to ensure a good life to the people. We therefore must say that

the human world keeps on both the empirical and normative dimensions in a cyclic, parallel, or even in interpenetrative order. So, it is impossible to make a separation between empiricism and normativism because of their interpenetrative nature.

The Essence of 'The Political'

Human mind is not seen through that we can see what is playing one's own mind. We can say it a 'hidden performing organ'. It can only be understood not by seeing the activities but systematic mind reading and calculative analysing of mind game, but still it is a difficult task. The past cumulative instances are helpful to make a sense on the present. But prediction is to large extent impossible because human nature is hardly unattainable and unpredictable. Human beings are political because they are self-conscious and self-calculative. This political nature makes human beings unique from the rest of the animal in the world. Human beings only think themselves as unique individuals among the group of individuals and act self-consciously not only for the groups, but also for one's own self. Human beings are always rational as they all are utility maximizers. Being a utility maximiser, human beings always evaluate their ends and means, if they found trouble with existing arrangements they postpone, change, or even deny their ends and means. Human beings are also political because of their diverse and contested self-interests. It would not be exaggeration to say that one of the common and recurrent features which can be found in social sciences in general and political science in particular is that they all deal with the idea of 'contestability'.³⁰ Contestability is not an anomalous phenomenon, it comes inherently due to the diverse and complex human behaviour that develops because of our diverse value system and our contrasting preferences, choices, which make human beings unique in the sense that they may see the same phenomenon but interpret it differently from one another because of their different value preferences. This idea of essential contestability, we do believe, shapes and constitutes the core of 'the political' that manifests in politics. In order to become any phenomena to be a theme of discussion in political science there must be a great deal of contestability regarding its nature and its content. For an example, we may ask, is there any necessity and viability of state? Is it possible for the utmost development of individual without any central political institution that

commands and also which is the supreme authority for resolving the conflict arises in society? For the classical Marxists, and anarchists, it is possible and even desirable to lead a good and happy life without any repressive, controlling, and commanding authority. The neo-liberals also shouted for some sort of diminution of state and promotion of market. They more or less, in their own way, took politics as an arena to move from conflict to develop cooperation. But the desirability of the state or any other central political mechanism arises to resolve the conflict arisen from the antagonistic nature of attitudes and behaviours which is an innate characteristic of human beings. Nevertheless an ample amount of definition of politics, we can say that politics is a state of affairs arises from the absence of general agreement. General agreement is hardly possible since human beings have different types of contradictory thinking, conflict over the resources, not only conflict over the material things but also conflict in establishing one's own will over the others. Absence of general agreement leads to conflict, struggle for power, exclusion, dominance, coercion, resistance, and so on and so forth. For that particular reason politics is everlasting. If we will be going to address in a better and convincing way all the things, we have to rest on the conceptual schema or theory. Thus Ball truly says "political theory could not die, at least while its parent politics lived."³¹ Here political theory implies because unless the normative framework, we cannot explain the set of practices which is called politics. This essentially contrasting value systems, preferences, norms of human beings what make the understanding of 'the political' and the study of politics difficult to completely adopting the methods and techniques, unlikely of natural sciences, in reaching to a final conclusion evading the 'logic of contestability.'

Conclusion: Understanding Politics in the age of Alternative Facts

The basic question that we explore and understand in this study is how to make the study of politics more practical as a discipline in contemporary times. Starting from the ancient Greco-Roman periods and remain unchallenged till the emergence of positivist tradition, the traditionalism indeed highlights some vital aspects of politics and more or less discussed the core ideas of politics like state, justice, liberty, rights, etc. In spite of that one of the recurrent and very common criticism against traditionalism is that

they were more of a lofty idealist, they prescribed more rather than accessing the practicality of politics. But at the same time we must admit that these ideas were the product of its own time when war and conflicts were the order of the day. Their recommendations were directed to achieve a perfect and just society. Traditionalism in the first half of the twenty first century was unable to save Europe from the devastation of the Great War; they failed to predict this event and at the same time was incapable to find the remedies. At the same time there was a growing dissatisfaction among social scientists regarding its methodology. As a result a new tradition emerged in social science – logical positivism that has its roots in Vienna Circle and the members were confident enough to discover the true task of 'philosophy of science'. Logical analysis was its aim and subject matter was the positive and empirical sciences in which only 'meaningful' statements or the statements having cognitive significance are to be considered. Meaningful statements only in sense of being either analytic (self-contradictions) or synthetic (factual; subject to verified or falsified by evidence).³² It denies the metaphysical and ontological existence. But, in political science, which deals with not about political practices of human beings within the domain of both state and society, but about the ontological dimensions of 'the political'. The concept of verifiability or falsifiability is contested due to the inherent nature of human beings. Another thing demands a brief discussion that, unlike sociology, political science both as an academic discipline and a practical study should not ignore the role of political institutions, formal as well as informal, in understanding politics that constrain and limit individual and group choices. This methodological approach has been popular in US political science academia since mid-1980s that attempts combining macro level and micro level understanding of politics. While macro level denotes the influences of formal structures, rules, and norms in shaping and determining individual's political preferences, micro level indicates individual and group political behaviour. A group of scholars, known as neoinstitutionalists, revives institutional analysis in order to understand the role of individuals and group behaviour in politics.³³ The neoinstitutionalism thus combines the interests of traditionalists in understanding the influence and role of structures, rules, norms, etc., simultaneously paying adequate attention upon individual and group actions as well

as intensions. Accessing the human directions in politics in contemporary times, we must acknowledge that facts, truths, information all are highly contested issues and bounded by context. As human perceptions, ways of thinking and understanding differ from each other, the idea of universality of facts or truths are highly problematic. Take for an example, those who supported the existence of state, may all agree that the first and foremost duty of the state is to uphold and protect the interests of individuals but there is not a single agreed definition that how it can be achieved, neo-liberals, communitarians, welfarist liberals have their own conception of delivering and securing the interests of individuals. These relative aspects of facts and truths must be kept in mind while referring any aspects of politics. The era of 'post-truth'³⁴ politics creates a difficulty to find out what is truth as the 'art of the lie' blurs not only the chasm between 'truth' and 'lie', but also places 'emotions' over the objective 'facts'. In this contemporary era of alternative facts, theory helps us in three ways – firstly, to differentiate among several alternative facts; secondly, to focus on the facts which are helpful; and thirdly, theory may be helpful as different theories may deal with the same phenomena but arrive at different conclusions. Here practicality does not imply complete detachment or altogether rejection of either normative or empirical aspects of politics rather amalgamation between the two. Neither excessive empiricism nor extreme normativism is sufficient to evaluate 'the political' nature of human beings. But it is also true this amalgamation is something of a herculean task especially in the current context due to our inclination of separating normative and empirical aspects of politics. But we must say that 'politics', both as a discipline and practice, changes over the time; it transforms its contents and adopts different methodologies to make the discipline more effective to address the ever-changing nature of politics as a set of practices in the milieu of contestability constituted by 'the political'.

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